

INTERPRETATION OF THE ISSUE OF TIME AND PERSONALITY IN AYDIN KHOJIYEVA'S LYRICS

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the period and personality of the People's Poet of Uzbekistan Aydin Khojiyeva. The war theme in the poet's lyrics is analyzed, as well as his poems describing the tragedy of the 70s and 80s of the last century. Poems written in a given period are methodologically analyzed and their specific aspects are studied.

In modern lyric poetry, the lyrical protagonist sets an example of high universal values, patriotism, purity, love for the country, the past and the future. A new spirit of nationalism has entered the works of the leading representatives of today's Uzbek poetry. The poets created a number of lyrical works on such topics as freedom and civic duty, conscience and devotion, humanity, morality, love. Our female poets Aydin Khojiyeva, Halima Khudoyberdiyeva, Gulchehra Nurullayeva, Zebo Mirzayeva were active in this creative process. Through the image of the poet, they have shown good results in imparting such qualities as spiritual perfection, devotion, and spiritual awakening in the hearts of those who live with the sufferings of the country and the nation.

"...the breath of the poetic epoch is the property of art created from the scenes of the processes that take place in the spiritual world of the man of that epoch in harmony with the lyrical heroic spiritual world. Therefore, it is unrealistic to imagine or study poetry in isolation from the character of the period." The psycho-psychological image of a child living with the feelings of homeland, nation, language and independence is skillfully presented in the works of the sweet-spoken poet Aydin Khojiyeva.

"This is ancient Karmana
Slippery roads. The desert where the
caravan pirates ... " My people, the flowers
that open in your heart

The sun went down between the districts!

The poem combines lyricism and
tragedy. The poet instills in him the pain of

the nation and the homeland. Roads are "slippery", and in the caravan of the Motherland "pirates" are destroying the nation, destroying spirituality and science. As a result, the "flowers" in the hearts of our people will die prematurely. Aydin Khojiyeva gives a special meaning to each image. By comparing the nationalist, patriotic hero who gave his life for freedom to a "flower", the poet achieves that now everyone understands him in familiar scenes, can understand the tragedy of that time in his own way.

He sacrificed his life for his homeland
But he remained in the torment of hell
His perceptive faith did not wane:
A war that bites a soldier like a snake,
Flying like a bird from its last breath -
Then he said, "Great Motherland."

In the language of a person who is fighting for the independence of the motherland with a weapon in his hand, the voice of "Motherland" resounds. The lyrical hero of the poem devotes all his energy, first of all, his faith, confidence and conscience to the independence of his homeland, and fights for the nation. Because the feeling of "Great Motherland" calls to overcome all the enmity of the world. The poet instills in him a sense of masculinity. It reminds us that independence has not been easy to achieve today, and that this land has shed the blood of thousands who fought for the freedom of their homeland.

Aydin Khojiyeva also managed to express the complexities of the period in a very delicate and profound way. The poet expresses the poetic expression in a clear and humane way:

Let's put fire in the heart of the earth!
The soldier was sweating profusely
The horse pulled the storm instead

Cotton is gold! Heaven is here!

The anguish of the poet's heart was the painful days of the "just" age for our people. When it is impossible to speak openly about it, the poet, as a child of a suffering people, dares to tell the truth of the time. During this period, cotton was more important than man, and the task of the man of the time was to plant cotton. Cotton is gold for him, cotton is heaven. At the same time, the poet truly burns from the suffering, sadness, and obedience of the nation. The poet concludes that the people of the homeland, who do not have freedom, are slaves, and expresses this through the description of the plight of the suffering people:

He was an immortal slave
She has five children - five worlds.
He did not serve anyone,
People's prayers are a blessing!

"...because slavery is death. The propensity for slavery is murder". Aydin Khojiyeva is a poet who deeply felt the tragedy of the time, the pain of her contemporaries and was able to incorporate these feelings into her work. It depicts a situation in which a person does not live as a human being, that is, a great human tragedy. In the poem, whether it is the spiritual and ideological essence, whether in the example of the whole nation, or in the example of one person, the appeal against any dependence or slavery comes to the fore. pulls awake. He is angry with the people who enslaved him in his homeland. In each line of the poem, the poet's experiences are expressed in the Uzbek way, and in some places the Uzbekness is exaggerated. Emphasizing that looking at the child as a whole world is an original aspect of the nature of our people gives this poem a powerful tone.

The light of guidance shone on my head,

When was a handful of stones?
From the sounds of lies,
An atheist crowd with their ears closed.

“...I am convinced that if a scholar wants to cover the history of twentieth-century Uzbek poetry, he cannot ignore Aydin's work.” Aydin Khojiyeva's nation, thinking about the fate of the Motherland, cares about its future. The poet does not criticize society by describing the hardships of people's lives. Time is a stone's throw away. As it changes, people's pride, generosity, and obedience increase. The vision of the people of the future is hopeless, the feelings of the artist are "deafened", that is, unable to remain indifferent to the fate of their contemporaries, deprived of their language, religion and freedom. Social changes and life situations can provide material for a poet to create lyrical works.

Each era has its own set of goals. The highest goal of the colonial man was freedom.

Freedom!

A flower in the heart,
I hurried like a child to cheer you up.
A thousand years of floods
I screamed and overflowed.
From the bedouins of the deserts
From the whirlwinds of the sun

From the losses of the era
Happiness without wings -
Freedom!

The lyrical protagonist is grateful to his ancestors for the freedom he came to his homeland, nation, history and great difficulties. Freedom is a high award given to the Uzbek people for their struggle for national liberation, restoration of historical and national values. In the poem, the lyrical hero becomes a bright expression of his devotion to the Motherland. Now his heart is full of gratitude for independence and confidence in the future. The poet gives her a special artistic content. The tragedy of the time was the slavery of thought in the dictatorship. Freedom is the happiness that "comes without wings" from constant oppression, loss and order.

In her lyrics, Aydin Khojiyeva describes both the past and the present with all her being and complexity. The poet creates a lyrical work by summarizing the themes of the restoration and promotion of human dignity, the motherland and independence. He approaches the choice of lyrical material based on the life of the period, demonstrates individual skill in the artistic and aesthetic interpretation of the experiences of his lyrical protagonist.

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